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EDITED BY

Tom Prickett,
Northumbria University, United Kingdom

REVIEWED BY

Lee Clift,
University of Strathclyde, United
Kingdom
Claire Rocks,
University of Warwick, United Kingdom

*CORRESPONDENCE

Pavel Smutny
✉ pavel.smutny@vsb.cz

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From rules to language models: a comparative study of chatbot learning assistants

Pavel Smutny* and Petra Schreiberova

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, VSB—Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czechia

Introduction: As AI-powered learning assistants become increasingly integrated into higher education, understanding their pedagogical impact across different technological designs is crucial. This study investigated the impact of a mobile chatbot learning assistant in a first-year university course, with attention to both its overall educational contribution and the effects of evolving chatbot technology.

Methods: This quasi-experimental, multi-cohort study followed five iterations of a first-year university course over a five-year period. A total of 240 students were naturally assigned by course enrollment to either a control group ($n = 113$), which used traditional learning methods, or an experimental group ($n = 127$), which received the same instruction supplemented by a mobile chatbot. Over the study period, the chatbot technology evolved from an initial decision-tree-based system to a more advanced Large Language Model (LLM)-driven version. The study therefore examined both the overall effects of chatbot support on learning outcomes, student perceptions, and motivation, and the differences associated with the two chatbot designs.

Results: The findings showed no statistically significant improvement in academic performance among students who used chatbot support compared with those in the control group. Nevertheless, students evaluated the chatbots positively, particularly in terms of usability, accessibility, and support outside regular school hours. Compared with the decision tree-based version, the LLM-driven chatbot showed a modest advantage in promoting engagement and offering more personalized support.

Discussion: Although chatbot integration did not lead to measurable gains in academic achievement, it was perceived as a valuable supplementary learning tool. The results suggest that AI chatbots may contribute more strongly to student experience and perceived support than to direct performance outcomes. In addition, the slight benefits of the LLM-driven version suggest that advances in chatbot design may enhance engagement and personalization in educational settings.

KEYWORDS

chatbots, decision trees, higher education, large language models, personal assistant

1 Introduction

The emergence of Large Language Model (LLM) powered chatbots, exemplified by ChatGPT's launch in November 2022, has fundamentally reshaped debates about teaching and learning in higher education. Academic interest has accelerated dramatically: Scopus publications on ChatGPT in education expanded from 1,329 articles in 2023 to over 4,370 by 2025, reflecting a sustained exponential trajectory. Concurrently, student adoption in United Kingdom has reached levels, with 92% of higher education students now employing AI-powered chatbots for academic work (Freeman, 2025). This rapid diffusion has extended

beyond ChatGPT to encompass a diverse ecosystem of competing models, including Claude, Google Gemini, DeepSeek, and Microsoft Copilot, each offering partly overlapping but also distinct affordances for the delivery of explanations, practice tasks, and feedback in learning.

In this article, the term “chatbot” is used as an umbrella label for text-based conversational agents that interact with students via natural-language interfaces. Within this broad category, the study focuses on two architectures that embody different pedagogical affordances. First, a decision tree-based (rule-based) chatbot presents predefined options, automates reminders, and guides learners through fixed interaction flows; it is well suited for structured repetition of core content but offers limited flexibility. Second, an LLM-based chatbot, instantiated through a custom configuration of ChatGPT, generates free-form responses conditioned on conversational context and an uploaded course-specific knowledge base, enabling more open-ended questions and adaptive explanations but also introducing new risks such as hallucinated or misleading responses. Clarifying this distinction is essential, because the central comparison in this study concerns how these two architectures function when deployed as supplementary learning assistants in the same course.

While the use of chatbots in higher education is a rapidly growing field of research, with studies demonstrating potential benefits for academic performance, motivation, and student engagement, the evidence remains mixed and often context-dependent (Bettayeb et al., 2024; Bouvier et al., 2026). Much of the existing literature focuses on modern LLM-based chatbots in short-term experimental settings (Bringula, 2024; Dunder et al., 2024; Modran et al., 2024; Polakova and Klimova, 2024) or offers broad overviews of their potential without direct empirical comparisons to other forms of AI assistants (Farrokhnia et al., 2024; Gill et al., 2024). There is a notable lack of longitudinal research that compares cohorts using established, rule-based chatbots with cohorts using newer LLM-based systems within the same authentic classroom environment. This study addresses this gap by directly evaluating and contrasting a rule-based chatbot used over four years (2019–2022) with a subsequent LLM-based chatbot used in 2024 in a real-world university STEM course, providing a more nuanced understanding of how these different AI technologies relate to student outcomes, including academic performance, motivation, and self-regulated learning.

It is common for people to gain new knowledge through social interaction by having conversations or discussions with colleagues, friends, or family members in everyday life (Tillema et al., 2015). Suitably structured conversational agents create a natural communication channel to support learning by creating a dialogue on a topic. This conversational agent can ask guided questions and engage users through verbal and non-verbal interventions. Conversational agents can also overcome natural human limitations, such as having limited patience or experiencing fatigue from long conversations (Chhibber et al., 2019).

In large classroom settings, teachers often have limited opportunities for meaningful one-on-one interactions with students, making it challenging to identify those who are shy or face barriers to face-to-face communication. As a result, shy students may go unnoticed if they do not participate actively in discussions or approach instructors with their concerns. For these students, chatbots are especially beneficial, offering a supportive format that accommodates those reluctant to engage in direct communication (Zhang et al., 2024).

The broader field of conversational AI encompasses a range of systems described as dialogue systems, intelligent tutoring systems, conversational agents, virtual agents, and chatbots (Archer et al., 1996; McTear, 2020). Over time, this field has evolved from rule-based systems specified through hand-crafted decision rules to statistical and neural dialogue systems that learn patterns from large datasets (Song and Xiong, 2021). The present study situates itself within this trajectory by contrasting a rule-based chatbot with a later LLM-based chatbot, both implemented as supplementary assistants in the same higher-education course.

As learning assistants, chatbots offer several advantages over purely human-mediated support (Kuhail et al., 2023). They are available around the clock and can be accessed from any location using a mobile device, giving students flexibility in when and where to engage with learning materials (Labadze et al., 2023). These digital assistants enable conversations to be conducted in small, manageable segments and allow for interruptions as needed (Pérez et al., 2020). Chatbots provide immediate feedback, patiently repeat information until it is understood, and create a safe learning environment free from preconceptions, expectations, or judgments, which helps reduce learning-related stress (Tsai et al., 2025). Furthermore, chatbots align with current educational trends toward automating elements of learning processes and supporting microlearning and adaptive learning environments (Silitonga et al., 2024; Terzieva et al., 2025).

The following three research questions were addressed in the study:

Research question 1: What effect does integrating a chatbot application have on a student’s learning achievements?

Research question 2: How do learning outcomes differ between students who interact with decision tree-based chatbots and those who use LLM-powered chatbots?

Research question 3: How do students in the experimental group perceive the usefulness and accept the use of the chatbot application on learning and motivation in a higher education course?

2 Literature review

Chatbots have been widely studied in the educational literature, but findings on their impact on learning are mixed, with studies reporting positive, null, and occasionally negative effects (Birenbaum, 2023; Huang et al., 2022; Ji et al., 2023; Kuhail et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2022; Pérez et al., 2020; Rapp et al., 2021; Salas-Pilco et al., 2022). In a 5th-grade science course, Deveci Topal et al. (2021) found no significant differences in achievement between chatbot-assisted and control groups, although students described the chatbot as engaging and useful for review. At the University of Granada, Castillo Valdivieso and Aguilar-Luzón (2021) reported that introducing a chatbot during tutorials coincided with notable changes in participation patterns and increases in course pass rates over previous years. Similarly, a study at the National University of Distance Education showed that students using a chatbot outside class improved their punctuation test scores for a university-admission exam and valued the tool’s flexibility and ease of use (Vázquez-Cano et al., 2021).

At the university level, Yin et al. (2021) examined a chatbot-based micro-learning system with first-year students and observed that both experimental and control groups improved, but that the chatbot group performed worse overall than those using traditional materials, despite appreciating self-paced study and immediate feedback. Chang et al. (2021) reported that an obstetric-vaccine chatbot supported deeper motivation and clearer understanding by providing rapid clarification of misconceptions. Chatbot-facilitated pre-conversations have also been shown to enhance discussion quality, critical thinking, and inquiry skills in group work (Goda et al., 2014), while Chang et al. (2021) found that chatbots could substitute for human tutors in a knowledge-based system, helping teachers identify areas where students struggled. Other studies have explored chatbots in cultural and language education, such as an AI tutor for Minoan civilisation that yielded promising results in integrating chatbots into ICT-based learning (Mageira et al., 2022), and a Telegram-based programming tutor where engagement varied but highlighted the importance of appropriate feedback and task difficulty (Alvarez et al., 2022).

Taken together, these studies highlight that the effects of educational chatbots are far from uniform. Some interventions report substantial gains in course completion or test performance when chatbots are tightly integrated with assessment and tutorial structures (Castillo Valdivieso and Aguilar-Luzón, 2021; Vázquez-Cano et al., 2021), whereas others find no significant differences in achievement despite positive student experiences (Chang et al., 2021; Deveci Topal et al., 2021). In at least one case, the chatbot-supported group performed worse than a comparison group using traditional methods, even though students valued the flexibility and immediacy of feedback (Yin et al., 2021). This pattern of mixed and sometimes contradictory findings suggests that the impact of chatbots depends strongly on how they are embedded in instruction, the nature of learning tasks, and actual student engagement. These contributions also span a wide range of educational levels and domains, from primary-school science and language learning to university-level nursing and programming courses. While this breadth demonstrates the versatility of chatbots, the current work is situated in a first-year, technically oriented higher-education course focused on spreadsheet-based data processing in Excel. In such technical and STEM-related contexts, chatbots are typically used as supplementary tools to support practice, troubleshooting, and access to course information rather than as stand-alone instructors.

The integration of generative AI, and ChatGPT in particular, into education has further expanded this landscape. Recent systematic reviews report that ChatGPT-based interventions can improve academic performance, support higher-order thinking, and enhance affective-motivational states, especially at university level, but they also point to methodological weaknesses and the need for robust assessment and power analysis (Deng et al., 2025). Other syntheses emphasise institutional and ethical dimensions, identifying challenges around technological integration, personalization and equity, data quality and security, and human-AI collaboration, and calling for clear policies and ongoing teacher training (García-López et al., 2025). A further systematic review highlights ChatGPT's promise for academic writing, lesson planning, and assessment, while warning against over-reliance and underscoring the importance of maintaining academic integrity in AI-supported environments (Salih et al., 2025).

Across these strands of work, most empirical studies evaluate a single chatbot configuration within a given course or context. Earlier educational chatbots are often rule-based or menu-driven systems with predefined dialogue flows, whereas recent deployments increasingly rely on LLM-based assistants that generate free-form responses (Giannakos et al., 2025; Kuhail et al., 2023). A small but growing number of studies begin to explore hybrid or comparative designs. For example, Fetрати et al. (2025) present a multi-chatbot mobile application for sexual health education that combines rule-based and generative chatbots, reporting high usability, positive user experience, and strong perceived educational value, with users particularly appreciating the LLM-based component. In a broader synthesis, Debets et al. (2025) systematically review 71 educational chatbot studies and show that recent work is increasingly dominated by chatbots built on modern platforms and, more recently, LLM-based technologies, while traditional rule-based systems receive comparatively less attention. Nevertheless, there remains very limited longitudinal evidence that directly contrasts rule-based and LLM-based chatbots within the same higher-education course and institution. In particular, few studies follow multiple cohorts as the underlying chatbot technology changes, making it difficult to disentangle the influence of chatbot architecture from cohort and contextual effects. The present study addresses this gap by comparing four cohorts using a decision tree-based chatbot (2019–2022) with a later cohort using an LLM-based chatbot (2024) in the same STEM course, alongside a control condition without chatbot access. This design enables a more nuanced examination of how different chatbot technologies function as supplementary learning assistants in an authentic higher-education setting.

3 Methodology

The use of a chatbot to support learning was implemented in a university course in the Czech Republic. A pre- and post-test quasi-experiment was conducted to assess the influence of the chatbot within the context of existing educational standards and practices. The course instructor is also the co-author of this paper and has over twelve years of experience teaching a data processing course using Excel. To mitigate potential bias from this dual role, all student data were anonymised prior to analysis and processed only after final semester grades were submitted. To ensure pedagogical consistency and eliminate inter-instructor variability, as the course is typically delivered by various teachers, all experimental and control sessions were conducted by the same instructor to ensure identical teaching methods and educational content across all groups.

The goal of the chatbot in the experimental group was to supplement the students' learning outside of school hours. The chatbot support was not intended to replace classroom lessons or supplement learning with new topics. The chatbot content was drawn exclusively from the same study materials, LMS assignments, and lectures available to all students; the intervention differed only in the mode of delivery, not in the information provided. In the framework of the conversation with the chatbot, the student received organizational information about the course, verified their knowledge through a quiz, or solved tasks using video tutorials. Specifically, this study included a control group and two experimental groups: one utilizing rule-based chatbots and the other

employing LLM-based chatbots. The chatbot was active for five of the fourteen weeks of the semester, covering only the Excel fundamentals component of the course; it was not used in any other part. At the end of the quasi-experiment, students completed a questionnaire to determine their experiences and opinions when using the chatbot. The quantitative method was applied both to the pre-test and post-test scores and to the results of the questionnaire. Figure 1 shows the progress of the quasi-experiment including the setup parameters. The following sections describe the details of the participants, the measured data and the chosen procedure. The collected data is quantitatively analysed to answer the three research questions above.

implementation, there was genuine uncertainty about whether chatbot-supported instruction would provide greater benefit than conventional teaching alone. This research was conducted using a quasi-experimental research method as the participants were not randomly assigned. Participants (Table 1) were grouped according to their scheduled classes. A total of 240 students were in this study, with 127 students in the experimental group learning with the support of the chatbot system, and the other 113 students in the control group learning via conventional teaching only. To reduce potential disadvantage to the control group, students in both groups were given the opportunity to retake the first test after the experiment if they were not satisfied with their original results.

3.1 Participants

The participants of this study were first-year university students, all enrolled in the same study programme within the same faculty at a single institution. Students were recruited from classes of a data processing course in Excel during the winter semester over the period of five years (2019–2022, 2024). Prior to any study activity, all students were asked to sign an informed consent form explaining the study’s purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without academic penalty. During the consent process, students were also informed that the study compared two instructional conditions and that, at the time of

3.2 Procedure and instruction

The study participants were split into two groups: a control group and an experimental group. The quasi-experiment was conducted over a period of five weeks and repeated five times over a five-year span. In the experimental group, a ten-minute discussion activity took place, and a chatbot became available as a learning support tool to assist students outside regular lectures and practical exercises. Students received an email with a link to access the chatbot. Between 2019 and 2022, a decision-tree chatbot was utilized to support student engagement. Each week,

TABLE 1 Number of participants over five cohorts.

Groups	2019	2020	2021	2022	2024	Total
Experimental group	32	18	24	21	32	127
Control group	15	22	26	16	34	113

the chatbot automatically sends students a reminder to take a voluntary quiz. This quiz, consisting of ten questions, reviewed the previous week's topic in preparation for the practical exercise. The feedback on the chatbot's usage by students was monitored and analysed using the analytical tools provided within the Chatfuel development platform. The collected data indicated whether students interacted with the chatbot and provided details about their dialogues. By 2024, LLM-based chatbots did not offer detailed usage statistics by students. To compensate for this limitation, questions about chatbot usage and engagement were included in the accompanying questionnaire to gather additional insights. It should be noted that the primary unit of analysis is the assigned group rather than individually confirmed engagement. While the available usage data indicate that the large majority of experimental-group students did interact with the chatbot, it cannot be entirely ruled out that some students engaged only minimally, or that control-group students independently consulted external tools, a possibility of particular relevance for the 2024 cohort given the widespread availability of general-purpose LLMs by that time. Findings should therefore be interpreted as reflecting the effect of access to and assignment to a chatbot-supported learning environment rather than individual usage intensity.

3.3 Pre- and post-tests

In the first week, students in both the control and experimental groups took a pre-test to assess their prior knowledge of Excel as a tool for data processing. The test consisted of ten multiple-choice items randomly selected from a 72-item question bank developed by the instructor. The question bank was structured around five key topics aligned with the course curriculum: spreadsheet functions, cell addressing, contingency tables and data validation, calculations from graphs, and matrix functions. The items were designed to directly assess the knowledge and skills covered in the course lectures and practical seminars. This direct alignment provides strong evidence of the test's content validity, ensuring it accurately reflects the curriculum and learning objectives. There was a 20-minute time limit for the test. An identical post-test was used in the 5th week to assess the student's improved knowledge after three weeks of lectures and practical exercises in both groups. The goal of the post-test was to examine the effectiveness of chatbot-based support compared to traditional learning. It was anticipated that both group participants' expertise would increase after finishing this Excel data processing course. By comparing the experimental group participants' academic achievements to those in the control group and using the pre-test as a covariate, this design enables the researcher to respond to the first research question.

3.4 Questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed to determine students' opinions about the chatbot application in the course and it was adapted from similar studies (Ogara et al., 2014; So, 2016). It consists of ten required items using the 4-Point Likert Scale and one optional open-ended question to express their opinion and experience with the chatbot. The reason to adopt 4-point scale was to prevent

respondents from selecting a neutral middle option. Also this scale can reduce cognitive load, making the survey-taking experience smoother for participants. The internal consistency of the adapted version was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha, which reached 0.81 for the main scale. The questionnaire was given to coincide with the last post-test for the experimental group.

The questionnaire included the following questions:

- Q1: Chatbot helped me sharpen my knowledge of the topic.
- Q2: Chatbot answered me meaningfully.
- Q3: The chatbot gave me information faster than other ways like asking in person, by email or phone.
- Q4: I used the chatbot during practical exercises or lectures.
- Q5: I found it convenient to read my study materials and take quizzes on my phone.
- Q6: I was able to use the chatbot without any limitations, regardless of factors like screen size, touch controls, internet speed, or battery status.
- Q7: Receiving chatbot alerts for lectures or upcoming tests outside of scheduled hours didn't bother me.
- Q8: I enjoyed a chat conversation.
- Q9: In my opinion, a chatbot has the potential to serve as a substitute for a human instructor.
- Q10: I recommend using a chatbot for other courses.

3.5 Chatbot development

Over the course of our quasi-experiment, spanning from 2019 to 2024, the landscape of creating custom chatbots evolved significantly. When we first considered integrating chatbots into an educational setting, the technological landscape was markedly different. For instance, there were very few large-scale language models available for the Czech language that could be seamlessly incorporated into chatbot systems. This posed a significant challenge: finding tools that were accessible, user-friendly, and did not require advanced programming knowledge, which was essential for successful implementation in an academic environment.

At that time, we selected the no-code bot-building platform Chatfuel to address these needs. Chatfuel allowed for the creation of rule-based chatbots, which we deployed within the Facebook Messenger mobile application. While its drag-and-drop interface was accessible, the platform required a moderate level of technical skill to use effectively. Although an advanced understanding of natural language processing (NLP) was not necessary, setting up the chatbot still required logical thinking, attention to detail, and familiarity with some technical concepts to build and manage decision trees. Through Chatfuel, we developed a decision-tree chatbot that was used from 2019 to 2022 to send weekly quiz reminders and support students in preparing for practical exercises (Figure 2). While the tool allowed for the automation of repetitive tasks, maintaining the chatbot required updates to decision branches and testing to ensure it could handle the variability of student interactions.

The main functional requirements for the rule-based chatbot (Figure 3) included deployment on the Messenger platform, utilizing a rule-based model for the knowledge base, and providing a straightforward, intuitive conversation flow. The

system supported multimedia content like text, images, and videos. Features included persuasive notifications to encourage interaction, a channel for students to contact learning assistants, and a humorous character named “Cell” with social media-inspired gestures and memes. To boost engagement, gamification elements, such as a scoring system, were also integrated.

By 2024, however, the process of creating custom chatbots had transformed dramatically with the rise of large-scale language models (LLMs). Platforms like ChatGPT, including custom-configured versions of the tool, enabled us to develop AI-driven chatbots that were significantly more dynamic and conversational. Unlike rule-based systems, LLM-based chatbots do not depend on predefined decision trees. Instead, they use advanced natural language processing to interpret and respond to user inputs with much greater flexibility. This change drastically reduced the effort needed to build and maintain the chatbot. The conversational design no longer required detailed manual programming for edge cases, and the chatbot could respond to a wide variety of queries using contextual understanding. This was a leap forward in terms of both time efficiency during development and the quality of student interactions.

The development of a custom chatbot using OpenAI's ChatGPTs enabled the creation of a highly personalized conversational agent tailored to a specific quasi-experimental context. The chatbot, named “Cell,” was designed with a distinct personality and role to align with the objectives of the study (Figure 4). Behavioural customization was implemented through explicit guidelines that defined how the chatbot should or

should not respond during interactions. To enhance user engagement, predefined conversation starters were incorporated, providing structured prompts to initiate dialogue effectively. Additionally, the chatbot's knowledge base was expanded by uploading domain-specific materials, including lecture slides, sample test questions, and course-related information such as grading policies and instructor contact details. This integration ensured the chatbot delivered accurate and contextually relevant responses. Following its configuration, “Cell” underwent iterative testing and refinement to optimize its performance before being deployed for the quasi-experimental study.

A comparison of the rule-based and LLM-based chatbots reveals that they possessed a distinct set of functions which, in turn, shaped the nature of student interactions. The initial rule-based chatbot, built on the Chatfuel platform, functioned as a structured information and task-delivery system operating on predefined decision trees. Its primary roles were to automate repetitive tasks, such as sending quiz reminders and guiding students through exercises using a fixed, multimedia-supported path. This resulted in highly guided student interactions, where conversations were navigated primarily through buttons and pre-set options, ensuring a predictable but rigid user experience. In contrast, the subsequent LLM-based chatbot, developed with a custom version of ChatGPT, functioned as a dynamic conversational partner. It leveraged advanced natural language processing to interpret free-form student queries and generate contextually relevant responses by drawing from an uploaded knowledge base of course materials. This shifted student interactions from a structured, menu-driven model to a flexible, open-ended dialogue, allowing for a much broader range of questions and a more natural, human-like conversation.

4 Results

The results are organized around three research questions and are presented separately for each of the three study conditions: the control group, the group using a decision tree-based (rule-based) chatbot, and the group using a large language model (LLM)-powered chatbot. First, we analyse how the use of a chatbot, either decision tree-based or LLM-powered, impacts students' learning achievement compared to the control group, with a focus on academic performance and educational outcomes. Second, we directly compare the learning outcomes between students who interacted with the decision tree-based chatbot and those who used the LLM-powered chatbot, highlighting differences in effectiveness between these two technologies. Finally, we examine students' perceptions of the chatbot, emphasizing aspects such as perceived usefulness, acceptance, and influence on motivation,

and we report these findings separately for the rule-based and LLM-based chatbot groups.

4.1 Chatbot impact on learning achievement

To investigate the potential correlation between chatbot utilization and improved academic performance, we conducted a quasi-experiment involving two distinct groups of students: experimental and control. This first phase of the quasi-experiment utilized a decision-tree based chatbot for the experimental group, designed to provide structured, personalized support and guidance. Data was collected over four academic years (2019–2022). At the onset of each semester, students were randomly allocated to either group. Both cohorts underwent a pre-test and, after three weeks, a post-test scored on a scale of

FIGURE 4 Translated dialogues of an LLM-based chatbot featuring: (a) starting page with prompt suggestions and an open text input field, (b) an example of a guided conversation, and (c) a knowledge practice quiz.

0–30. The dataset comprised 95 observations from the experimental group and 79 from the control group, which were subsequently analyzed. To improve clarity, we categorized the results into six tiers with five points each and generated histograms (Figure 5). The data distribution appeared to be consistent for both exams within each group.

Students most often scored 6–25 points in the pre-test (90% students) and half of the students had a maximum of 15 points. Both groups improved their results in the post-test. 89% students from the experimental group obtained at least 16 points and it was even 95% of the students in the control group. The basic numerical characteristics together with the corresponding box plots are presented in Table 2; Figure 5. The box plots illustrate the distribution of scores in the control and experimental groups for the pre-test and post-test (Figure 6). Each group includes two box plots representing the scores for

both tests. This visualization enables comparison not only between the groups but also within each group.

To examine learning outcomes within both groups, we compared pre-test and post-test mean scores. Regarding the comparison between groups, the *p*-values for the pre-test and post-test were 0.71 and 0.16, both greater than 0.05. This indicates that no statistically significant differences were found between the groups. The effect sizes were small (Cohen's *d* = 0.05 and 0.25), so the differences between the groups can be considered minor.

Although the decision-tree-based chatbot did not demonstrate a consistent effect for all students, the results suggest that this approach can still be useful for learning in different ways. Further research should focus on how individual student characteristics and their level of engagement influence the effectiveness of this tool.

FIGURE 5 The histograms display pre-test and post-test data for decision-tree-based chatbot.

TABLE 2 Descriptive statistics: main numerical characteristics for all tests.

Groups	<i>n</i>	\bar{x}	\tilde{x}	<i>s</i>	Min	Max	Skewness
Pre-test—experimental group	95	15.8	15	6.2	3	30	0.015
Pre-test—control group	79	16.1	15	6.0	3	30	-0.090
Post-test—experimental group	95	23.2	24	5.1	9	30	-0.565
Post-test—control group	79	24.3	24	4.6	9	30	-0.701

The second phase of the quasi-experiment introduced a Large Language Model (LLM)-powered chatbot, specifically custom ChatGPTs, for the experimental group. This phase followed a similar setup to the first, but data were collected over a single semester in the autumn of 2024. Both groups of students (experimental and control) completed the same pre-test at the start of the semester, and after a three-week interval, a post-test scored on a scale of 0–30. The LLM-powered chatbot enabled more dynamic, context-aware interactions by leveraging advanced natural language processing to provide personalized learning support and adaptive feedback.

For clarity, the results were grouped into six 5-point classes and visualized as histograms (Figure 7). The distributions of both pre- and post-tests appear similar across the two groups (Table 3; Figure 8). The experimental group that used the LLM chatbot showed a higher mean improvement (5.4 vs. 3.9) and greater variability in results. The higher median (7.5) suggests that improvement was more pronounced for a larger proportion of students in the experimental group.

A separate paired *t*-test was conducted for each group to examine changes between pre- and post-test. In both cases, the *p*-values (0.0005 for the experimental group; 0.00012 for the

TABLE 3 Descriptive statistics: main numerical characteristics for all tests.

Groups	<i>n</i>	\bar{x}	\tilde{x}	<i>s</i>	Min	Max	Skewness
Pre-test—experimental group	32	17.4	18	7.2	3	30	−0.19
Pre-test—control group	34	18.9	18	5.9	9	30	0.14
Post-test—experimental group	32	22.9	24	6.4	6	30	−1.16
Post-test—control group	34	22.9	24	6.1	6	30	−1.16

control group) were below the significance threshold of 0.01. This suggests that both groups showed statistically significant improvement over time.

Thus, the paired *t*-test supports the conclusion that the improvements observed in both groups are not due to chance and that both groups showed significant progress over the course of the quasi-experiment. However, since both groups improved significantly, this effect cannot be attributed solely to the chatbot’s presence.

Two independent two-sample *t*-tests were performed to directly compare the groups—one for the pre-test and one for the post-test.

For the pre-test, the *p*-value was 0.3776 (Cohen’s *d* = 0.23), indicating that there was no statistically significant difference between the groups at the start of the quasi-experiment. This suggests that the groups were roughly comparable in terms of initial knowledge.

For the post-test, the *p*-value was 0.9885 (Cohen’s *d* = 0), indicating no significant difference between the groups. The effect size was small in both cases.

These findings show no statistically significant difference in post-test outcomes between the experimental and control groups, indicating comparable progress in both by the conclusion of the quasi-experiment. Consequently, based on the results of both assessments, it can be concluded that performance levels were similar across the two groups at the start and end of the study.

4.2 Comparative analysis of decision tree and LLM-powered chatbots

We used independent-samples *t*-tests to examine differences in observed outcomes between two temporally separated cohorts

exposed to different chatbot implementations. The goal was to examine whether differences in observed outcomes could be identified between cohorts (Figure 9). The cohorts were recruited in different time periods (2019–2022 vs. 2024), but the primary focus was on differences between approaches. No statistically significant differences were found in mean post-test scores between the two cohorts (*p* = 0.3713; Cohen’s *d* = 0.067). Similarly, the analysis of score differences between the pre-test and post-test did not reveal a significant difference (*p* = 0.1334). However, the medium effect size (Cohen’s *d* = 0.4) may indicate a potentially meaningful difference that was not detected as statistically significant.

A descriptive analysis of score distributions provides additional context. In the cohort assessed in 2024, the distribution shows a slightly different pattern, with the highest proportion of students (31.3%) scoring between 11 and 15 points. At the same time, a larger proportion of students achieved higher scores, with 18.8% scoring in the ranges of 21–25 and 26–30 points. Overall, in both cohorts, most students achieved mid-range scores (11–15 points). However, the 2024 cohort shows a higher proportion of students in the top score range (21–30 points) than the 2019–2022 cohort.

When comparing the distributions of score improvements between the two cohorts (2019–2022 and 2024), several differences are evident (Figure 10). In the 2024 cohort, a slightly higher percentage of students improved by 1–15 points, while fewer students showed no improvement. Specifically, 73.7% of students improved within this range, compared to 65.6% in the 2019–2022 cohort. At the same time, the proportion of students who did not improve was lower in the 2024 cohort (18.9%) than in the 2019–2022 cohort (28.1%).

Overall, both approaches appear to be associated with improved student outcomes, and the differences between

FIGURE 8 Box plots comparing pre-test and post-test score distributions between control and experimental groups, showing similar learning gains in both conditions with no significant difference between LLM-powered chatbot and traditional instruction methods.

FIGURE 9 The frequency distribution of the pre-test and post-test scores for the two different chatbot versions.

cohorts are relatively small. Although the results in the 2024 cohort appear slightly more favorable, the lack of statistically significant differences and the study’s limitations suggest that the findings may have been influenced by other factors, particularly cohort differences that may not be directly

related to the chatbot technology itself. One limitation to interpreting the results is also the relatively small sample size, especially in the LLM-based cohort, which may have reduced statistical power and made it more difficult to detect smaller effects.

FIGURE 10 The frequency distribution of the differences between experimental tests.

4.3 Student perceptions of chatbot usefulness

A total of 92 respondents (31 + 15 + 24 + 22) from the 2019–2022 cohort completed the questionnaire. Almost 90% of students enjoyed the chatbot for their learning and would

recommend it. Most students did not consider it a substitute for a teacher; they used it primarily to support their existing knowledge. Students particularly appreciated the chatbot’s user-friendliness, quick responses, and the usefulness of its answers. It seems that using the chatbot brings variety to the learning process and is highly valued by students (Figure 11).

FIGURE 11 Absolute frequencies of responses from a questionnaire on the decision-tree based chatbot used by students in the course, based on data collected from 92 respondents in the 2019–2022 cohort.

A total of 36 respondents from the experimental group filled in answers for the monitored period 2024. The survey results (Figure 12) indicate that students generally had a positive experience with the chatbot. Most respondents (28) agreed that it helped refine their knowledge, and the majority (25) found its answers meaningful, with 7 strongly agreeing. The chatbot was also perceived as responsive, with 18 students agreeing and 13 strongly agreeing that it provided quick answers. However, opinions on its usefulness in the classroom were more divided, with 17 agreeing and 9 disagreeing, while 6 strongly disagreed. Students appreciated the chatbot’s accessibility on mobile and web, with 22 agreeing and 5 strongly agreeing. While most students (16) disagreed that the chatbot could replace a teacher, a small number (6) saw potential in this role. Overall, the chatbot was well-received, with 19 students agreeing and 16 strongly agreeing that they would recommend its use, and only one student disagreeing.

Despite all participants responding to the same set of items using a four-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree), differences in response patterns were observed. To facilitate comparison between the two analyzed approaches, the relative frequencies of responses are presented in Tables 4, 5. In both cohorts, the overall perception of the chatbot was largely positive. The majority of respondents selected either ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ for most questionnaire items, indicating general satisfaction with the chatbot experience, regardless of the underlying technology. A key difference emerged in the perception of usability without limitations. In the first cohort (decision tree), 94% of participants agreed that the chatbot was usable without

limitations, compared with 64% in the second cohort. Interestingly, although LLMs are typically more advanced, participants in the second cohort appeared to evaluate the system more critically, possibly due to higher expectations or more varied interactions. When asked whether the chatbot could serve as a potential substitute for a human, both groups predominantly disagreed. However, the students from the second cohort (LLM-based) were slightly more open to the idea, with 20% agreeing or strongly agreeing, compared to only 6% in the first cohort. A high percentage of students in both cohorts indicated that they would recommend the chatbot for use in other courses. This item received 91% agreement in the first cohort and 97% in the second one, reflecting strong support for continued chatbot use regardless of system type. The results suggest that while both systems were well received, students interacting with the LLM chatbot reported higher engagement and conversational satisfaction but were more critical of its limitations. In contrast, the decision tree chatbot was perceived as more predictable and easier to use, which may have led to more strongly positive responses in items related to usability. These findings offer insights into user expectations and experiences when interacting with chatbots of varying complexity, and may inform future design decisions for educational AI tools.

5 Discussion

Our study examines how chatbots can help students practice the knowledge they acquire from lectures and seminars, as well

TABLE 4 Relative frequencies of responses from a questionnaire on the decision-tree based chatbot, based on data collected from 92 respondents in the 2019-2022 cohort.

Response	Helped sharpen knowledge	Answered meaning-fully	Gave info faster	Used during practicals/lectures	Convenient on phone	Usable without limitation	Alerts didn't bother me	Enjoyed conversation	Potential substitute for human	Recommend for other courses
Strongly agree	0.25	0.28	0.28	0.03	0.32	0.45	0.45	0.18	0.01	0.38
Agree	0.61	0.62	0.53	0.28	0.61	0.49	0.39	0.70	0.05	0.53
Disagree	0.10	0.08	0.17	0.41	0.05	0.04	0.11	0.10	0.54	0.05
Strongly disagree	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.27	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.39	0.03

TABLE 5 Relative frequencies of responses from a questionnaire on the LLM-based chatbot, based on data collected from 36 respondents in the 2024 cohort.

Response	Helped sharpen knowledge	Answered meaning-fully	Gave info faster	Used during practicals/lectures	Convenient on phone	Usable without limitation	Alerts didn't bother me	Enjoyed conversation	Potential substitute for human	Recommend for other courses
Strongly agree	0.03	0.19	0.36	0.11	0.14	0.22	0.33	0.08	0.03	0.44
Agree	0.78	0.69	0.50	0.25	0.61	0.42	0.42	0.83	0.17	0.53
Disagree	0.17	0.11	0.11	0.47	0.25	0.33	0.19	0.08	0.44	0.03
Strongly disagree	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.17	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.36	0.00

as provide them with support and information about the course. This study positions chatbots as supplementary learning support rather than as primary instruction, a design choice that is consistent with several prior studies but still less common than broader chatbot-instruction models (Fidan and Gencel, 2022; Jasin et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2022; Lee and Yeo, 2022). In comparison, other studies (Huang et al., 2022; Ji et al., 2023; Kuhail et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2022; Salas-Pilco et al., 2022) have found that chatbots can effectively enhance students' learning outcomes by providing them with immediate feedback, personalized learning experiences, and access to learning resources. However, our research emphasizes the importance of chatbots as complementary tools to help students reinforce and practice the knowledge they acquire from other sources. The main contribution of this study is therefore not a demonstrated improvement in test scores, but rather evidence that students perceived both chatbot types as helpful, accessible, and convenient for course support.

In addressing our first research question, the quantitative results did not show statistically significant learning gains attributable to chatbot use, suggesting that any benefits were more visible in student perceptions than in test performance. This non-significant result requires critical examination, and several factors could explain this outcome. First, the limited intervention scope, where the chatbot was implemented as an optional, supplementary tool for a single course, may have been insufficient to meaningfully alter final test scores. Second, regarding the level and nature of student engagement, we lack granular data on the depth of their interactions. Students may have used the chatbot for brief, superficial queries rather than for sustained, deliberate practice, meaning the positive perception may stem from its convenience rather than from a deepening of cognitive processing. Our findings do not provide strong evidence of improved learning outcomes from chatbot access alone, but they do show that students valued the chatbot as a convenient and accessible support tool. Our research makes a valuable addition to the current body of literature regarding the implementation of chatbots in educational settings (Essel et al., 2022; Sarosa et al., 2022), with a specific focus on their role as learning assistants. A meta-analysis (Wu and Yu, 2024) reported a generally large positive effect of chatbots on learning outcomes, with stronger effects in higher education, our results indicate that chatbot access alone was not sufficient to produce measurable gains in this course, likely because of the limited scope and optional use of the intervention.

For our second research question, we compared learning outcomes between students using decision tree-based chatbots (2019–2022) and those using LLM-powered chatbots (ChatGPTs) in 2024. Both tools showed similar overall impacts on student performance, with a slight positive trend in the 2024 period when ChatGPTs were used. The LLM-based cohort showed a descriptively smaller share of students with no improvement, but this pattern was not statistically significant and cannot be separated from cohort differences or other contextual factors. Our results suggest that for well-defined practice tasks, a structured, rule-based system may be almost as effective. The slight improvement seen with the LLM may be attributable to higher engagement due to its novelty and conversational prowess. However, the lack of a significant gap

could indicate that for the specific task of reinforcing learned material, the guided, predictable paths of a decision-tree chatbot provide sufficient scaffolding. The open-ended nature of an LLM, while powerful, might not have been fully leveraged by students for this learning objective and could even introduce distractions.

This finding corresponds with recent research on chatbot architectures. Decision tree chatbots operate on a flowchart-like structure of predetermined questions and answers, providing structured guidance but lacking the flexibility of LLM-powered systems. Recent studies (Cai et al., 2024; Puertas et al., 2023) indicate that LLM-powered chatbots can process and understand user queries more effectively than traditional methods and can adapt to specific tasks using relatively small amounts of task-specific data.

Our third research question investigated student perceptions of chatbot usefulness and acceptance in higher education. During the quasi-experiment, students expressed enthusiasm about using a chatbot in their learning process. According to student feedback, the chatbot helped reinforce knowledge, enabled practice of material covered in lectures and seminars, and provided support and information about the course. The students also appreciated the interactivity and personalized feedback provided by the chatbot, which they felt improved their engagement and motivation in the learning process. These findings align with recent research on student perceptions of AI chatbots in education. Studies examining learners' perceptions of ChatGPT have found that student satisfaction and perceived usefulness significantly shape attitudes toward chatbots (Almogren et al., 2024; Almulla, 2024; Polyportis & Pahos, 2025; Raman et al., 2024; Šedlbauer et al., 2024).

Our comparison of the three conditions—no chatbot, rule-based (decision tree), and LLM-powered chatbot—revealed no significant differences in student learning outcomes. The no chatbot group relied solely on traditional instruction, with no automated assistance. The rule-based chatbot provided structured, predictable responses to common queries, reinforcing factual knowledge within a fixed framework. In contrast, the LLM-powered chatbot offered flexible, adaptive support and could respond to a wide variety of student inputs. Despite these functional differences, both chatbots were implemented as optional, supplementary aids rather than as central instructional tools. This limited integration likely reduced the observable impact of even the more advanced LLM system. Although students perceived the LLM chatbot as more interactive and engaging, these advantages did not result in measurable learning gains. These findings underscore the importance of aligning chatbot capabilities, instructional design, and assessment methods more closely to optimize the benefits of AI in education.

Given this context, there are several practical implications for educators and institutions. Rather than pursuing broad implementation, institutions should strategically deploy chatbots where they can be most effective, such as serving as first-line support tools in courses with high volumes of factual content to handle common inquiries. This frees up human instructors to address more complex, higher-order thinking challenges. The effective use of chatbots also requires teacher training on how to integrate these tools into course design, including curating effective practice questions and teaching students how to

interact with them in a productive manner. Widespread adoption also necessitates a robust ethical framework. Key considerations include student data privacy, the potential for LLM-based chatbots to provide incorrect information, and the risk that students may become overly dependent on AI, which could hinder the development of independent research and critical thinking skills.

6 Limitations and future directions

The research was conducted in a single course at a public university in a European context, which supports close observation of authentic classroom practice while naturally limiting generalizability.

As a quasi-experimental study without random assignment, the results should be interpreted as evidence from a real classroom setting rather than as proof of causal effects. The multi-year structure of the study also means that the cohorts differed across academic years, so cross-cohort comparisons should be read as indicative rather than definitive. In addition, group sizes varied between conditions, which may have affected statistical power, especially in the smaller cohorts. Student engagement with the chatbot was not identical across participants, and differences in usage intensity may have contributed to variation in individual outcomes.

Future investigations could build on this foundation by exploring comparable implementations across different institutions, academic disciplines, and student populations to strengthen external validity, while incorporating randomization where feasible, more consistent group sizes, and richer interaction data such as engagement frequency, session duration, and question types.

7 Conclusions

This quasi-experimental study suggests that educational chatbots can function as useful supplementary tools, but the evidence for direct impact on learning outcomes is limited. By directly comparing decision tree-based and LLM-powered chatbots used specifically for practice and support, we found that both approaches were associated with increased student engagement and perceived learning support, yet neither substitutes the irreplaceable role of human educators.

The added value of our research lies in highlighting the nuanced impact of chatbot integration: effectiveness may depend less on chatbot architecture alone than on thoughtful alignment with course objectives and teaching methods. For practitioners, this means that successful adoption may benefit from targeted integration, including the use of chatbots to answer routine queries or reinforce key skills, while maintaining student autonomy.

Institutional adoption should therefore be framed cautiously, with priority given to support functions and further controlled research rather than broad claims about effectiveness.

The results of our study highlight the significance of careful deployment and ongoing evaluation when introducing AI technologies in education. Further research is needed to

examine how such tools can be implemented effectively across different educational contexts.

Data availability statement

The datasets presented in this study can be found in online repositories. The names of the repository/repositories and accession number(s) can be found below: https://osf.io/a9buz/?view_only=cdb50f5c8f2048748519325d9b1d48aa.

Ethics statement

According to the “Ethical framework for research” issued by the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (the primary governing body for our field of research), there is an explicit exemption from informed consent for research studying educational methods or conducting classroom teaching or anonymous questioning (article 6.2.)—see https://msmt.gov.cz/file/35846_1_1/. Our study’s methodology aligns with these criteria. Nevertheless, as part of the research and transparency of the process, we requested and obtained written informed consent from all participants. Crucially, this ethical framework does not require approval from the ethics committee of the institution in this case either, as the conditions for the exemption are met and informed consent was still obtained for due diligence. The studies were conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Author contributions

PSm: Supervision, Validation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Resources, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. PSc: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly Premium and Perplexity Pro in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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